

ATTITUDE OF SOYBEAN GROWERS TOWARDS USE OF WEEDICIDES

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Abstract

The present study was conducted in Marathwada region of Maharashtra during the year 2021-23 with the objective to study attitude of soybean growers towards use of weedicides. Four talukas and three villages from each taluka, selected randomly from Parbhani district for the study. Ten soybean growers selected randomly from each selected villages of four talukas, in this way the total respondents 120 considered for the present investigation. Collected data was analyzed, classified and tabulated. Statistical tools such as frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation and coefficient correlation were used to interpret findings and draw conclusions.

The results regarding soybean growers according to their attitude towards use of weedicides in soybean crop indicated that majority (67.50%) of the soybean growers had favourable attitude towards weedicides use in soybean crop, whereas 16.67 per cent of the farmers had less favourable attitude and 15.83 per cent had highly favourable attitude towards utilization of weedicides.

Keywords: - Attitude, Soybean growers, Weedicides

Introduction

Weed is a serious problem in crop production and responsible for making enormous losses in crop fields. They take plant nutrients, water, fertilizers and solar energy which should be available to the main crop. They compete with the crop for space harbors pest and diseases and have allelopathic effects on crop they reduce quality of produce and increase cost is a serious problem in crop production and responsible for making enormous losses in crop fields.

Insect pests and plant diseases cause considerable damage to agricultural crop but losses caused by weeds are even more. Many research workers have tried to assess the losses caused by weeds due to reduction in any yield and the removal of plant food from the soil. The estimated losses in crop yield alone range from 5.00 per cent in clean cultivation of fields to over 70.00 per cent in neglected fields depending upon the degree of weed infestation.

In Marathwada region of Maharashtra soybean and cotton are major crops grown in kharif season by farmers. Area under soybean crop in Marathwada is 10021.72 Hectare, production 12413.71 quintals, productivity 1040.56 kg/ha. Soybean crop can be grown on diverse type of soil, duration of crop varies from 80-120 days depending on the varieties, majorly cultivated under rainfall condition in kharif season. (Pathrikar *et al.* 2022).

Soybean [*Glycine max (L.) Merrill*] is the world's most important seed legume which contribute (25.00%) of the global edible oil about two third of the world protein concentrate for the livestock feeding and its valuable ingredients in the formulated feed poultry and fishery. Soybean is fastest growing crop in India which replaced the crops like maize, cotton and pulses.

Soybean is the richest source of protein with (40.00%) protein and (20.00%) oil. Also, soybean crop used for preparation of various snacks and food recipe. (I.C. Baianu *et al.* 2012).

In cultivation of soybean crop weed is one of the major problems and affecting productivity. Weedicides is one of the control measures to control the weeds in soybean crop and minimizes losses due to weeds. Attitude is the degree of positive or negative disposition/association towards an innovation, object, programme, enterprise etc. An attitude refers to a set of emotions, beliefs and behaviours towards the particular object, person, thing or event. Attitudes are often the results of experience or upbringing and they can have powerful influence over behaviour. Attitude is a way of feeling or acting towards the person, thing or situation.

Methodology

NAAS Rating – 04.17

From the Marathwada region of Maharashtra Parbhani district was selected for the study, Parbhani district has nine tahsils in which Manwat, Parbhani, Jintur and Pathari tahsils selected randomly and three villages from each tahsil have been selected randomly for the present study. The ten respondents selected randomly from three randomly selected villages of four tehsils. In this way, the total 120 respondents were considered for the present investigation. Ex-post facto design of social research was used for the present investigation.

Result

Attitude of soybean growers towards the use of weedicides in soybean crop.

Statement wise distribution of soybean growers according to their attitude towards use of weedicides

The results regarding soybean growers according to their attitude towards use of weedicides in soybean crop in table no 1 indicated that, (60.84%) soybean growers had strongly agreed on chemical weed control is best method of weed control, (35.83%) of the soybean grower had agree, while (3.33%) of the soybean growers are undecided.

Significant percentage (51.67%) of the soybean growers had disagree that use of weedicides is costly method of weed control, followed by (43.33%) of the respondents had strongly disagree, while (5.00%) undecided.

Large majority (70.00%) of soybean growers had agree about chemical weed control is time saving method of weed management and (30.00%) had strongly agree with the statement.

More than three fifth 65.00 per cent of soybean growers had strongly agree about use of weedicides save the cost of labour, whereas (26.67%) of respondents had agree and (8.33%) were undecided.

Nearly equal percentage (36.67%) and (34.17%) of the soybean grower had undecided and disagree about hand weeding is sufficient for weed control in soybean crop, followed by (18.33%) were strongly disagree and also nearly equal percentage (5.83%) and (5.00%) of the soybean grower had agree and strongly disagree.

Majority (64.17%) of the soybean growers had agreed about optimum moisture is needed in the soil for weeding, while 20.00 per cent of respondents were strongly agree and 15.83 per cent were undecided.

Nearly (45.83%) of the soybean growers had disagree about excess use of weedicides have negative impact on the soil fertility, whereas 50.00 per cent were strongly disagree regarding the statement and 4.17 per cent were undecided.

Flat pan nozzle is used for spraying of weedicides in soybean had

undecided by (62.50%) of the soybean growers, 34.17 per cent were agreed while 3.33 per cent were strongly agreed.

Regarding hand weeding along with use of weedicides is beneficial were agreed by 41.67 per cent of the soybean growers followed by 30.00 per cent strongly agree, whereas 27.50 per cent were undecided and 0.83 per cent were strongly disagree.

Statement technical support is easily available for operating high volume sprayer had undecided by the 30.83 per cent of the soybean growers, whereas (23.33%), (20.00%), (17.50%) and (8.33%) of the soybean growers were disagree, agree, strongly disagree and strongly agree.

More than half (55.83%) of the respondents were strongly disagree regarding excess use of weedicides for weed control is not eco-friendly method of weed control, whereas (34.17%) of the soybean growers were disagree and (10.00%) were undecided.

Safety precautions are needed to be taken while handling sprayer had strongly agreed by the 63.33 per cent of the soybean growers while 35.00 per cent were agreed, whereas 1.67 per cent were undecided.

More than half (55.83%) of the soybean growers had agreed on chemical weed control is better method of the weed management than any other methods, whereas 42.50 per cent of the respondents were strongly agree and same percentage *i.e.* 0.83 were undecided and disagree.

Drift hazards occur due to high wind velocity had strongly disagreed by the soybean growers 34.17 per cent of the soybean growers while 31.67 per cent were disagree and 28.33 per cent, 5.83 per cent were undecided and agree.

More than half (55.00%) of the soybean growers had strongly agreed on the hand compression sprayer is used in soybean crop is beneficial while 44.17 per cent of the respondents were agree, whereas statement is disagreed by the 0.83 per cent of the soybean growers.

In case of the statement soybean seeds must be free from weed seed during sowing had strongly agreed by (52.50%) of the soybean growers, while 34.17 per cent had agreed, whereas 13.33 per cent were undecided.

Nearly half (48.33%) of the soybean growers were agreeing about sprayer must be cleaned after use of weedicides and 47.50 per cent were strongly agree, whereas 3.33 and 0.83 per cent were undecided and strongly disagree.

More than half that is 55.00 per cent of the soybean growers were disagree for the statement that during high wind speed spraying of weedicides is difficult operation, whereas 44.17 and 0.83 per cent were strongly disagree and undecided.

Overall attitude of the soybean growers towards use of weedicides

From the table 2, it was clear that, majority (67.50%) of the soybean growers had favourable attitude towards weedicides use in soybean crop, whereas 16.67 per cent of the farmers had less favourable attitude and 15.83 per cent had highly favourable attitude towards utilization of weedicides.

The findings of this investigation are aligned with those of a previous study done by Dhawale (2019), Kaur *et al.* (2014) and Korde (2017).

Conclusion

Majority 67.50 per cent of the respondents had favourable attitude towards use of weedicides in farming system, whereas 16.67 per cent of the farmers had less favourable attitude and 15.83 per cent had highly favourable attitude towards use of weedicides in farming system.

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Table 1: Statement wise distribution of soybean growers according to their attitude towards use of weedicides

Sr. No.	Statements	SA		A		UD		DA		SDA	
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
1	Chemical weed control is best method of weed control.	73	60.84	43	35.83	4	3.33	0	0.00	0	0.00
2*	Use of weedicides is costly method of weed control in soybean	0	0.00	0	0.00	6	5.00	62	51.67	52	43.33
3	Chemical weed control is time saving method of weed management.	36	30.00	84	70.00	0	0.00	0	0	0	0.00
4	Use of weedicides save the cost of labour.	78	65.00	32	26.67	10	8.33	0	0	0	0.00

5	Hand weeding is sufficient for weed control in soybean.	6	5.00	7	5.83	44	36.6 7	41	34.1 7	22	18.33
6	Optimum moisture is needed in the soil for weeding.	24	20.0 0	77	64.1 7	19	15.8 3	0	0.00	0	0.00
7*	Excess use of weedicides have negative impact on the soil fertility.	0	0.00	0	0.00	5	4.17	55	45.83	60	50.00
8	Flat pan nozzle is used for spraying of weedicides in soybean.	4	3.33	41	34.17	75	62.50	0	0.00	0	0.00
9	Hand weeding along with use of weedicides is beneficial.	36	30.0 0	50	41.6 7	33	27.5 0	0	0.00	1	0.83
10	Technical support is easily available for operating high volume sprayer.	10	8.33	24	20.0 0	37	30.8 3	28	23.33	21	17.50
11*	Excess use of weedicides is not eco-friendly method of weed control.	0	0.00	0	0.00	12	10.00	41	34.17	67	55.83
12	Safety precautions are needed to be taken while handling sprayer.	76	63.33	42	35.00	2	1.67	0	0.00	0	0.00
13	In soybean crop chemical weed management is better than older method weed control.	51	42.5 0	67	55.8 3	1	0.83	1	0.83	0	0.00
14	Drift hazards occur due to high wind velocity.	0	0.00	7	5.83	34	28.33	38	31.67	41	34.17
15	Hand compression sprayer in soybean crop is beneficial.	66	55.00	53	44.17	0	0.00	1	0.83	0	0.00
16	Soybean seeds must be free from weed seeds during sowing.	63	52.50	41	34.17	16	13.33	0	0.00	0	0.00
17	Sprayer must be cleaned after use of weedicides.	57	47.5 0	58	48.3 3	4	3.33	0	0.00	1	0.83
18*	During high wind speed spraying of weedicides is difficult operation.	0	0.00	0	0.00	1	0.83	66	55.00	53	44.17

*Shows negative Statements

SA-Strongly Agree, A-Agree, UD-Undecided, DA-Disagree SDA-Strongly Disagree.

Table -2 Overall attitude of the soybean growers towards use of weedicides

Sr. No.	Category	Frequency	Per cent
1	Less favourable (up to 70)	20	16.67
2	Moderately favourable (71 to 78)	81	67.50
3	Highly favourable (79 & above)	19	15.83
	Total	120	100.00